

ENHANCING CENTRAL ASIAN REGIONAL COOPERATION AND FOREIGN POLICY IN “UZBEKISTAN – 2030” STRATEGY

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Uzbekistan is implementing transformative reforms under its ambitious national development strategy, the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, which was adopted in September 2023.²⁷ The strategy focuses on improving living conditions, fostering a fair and modern state that serves its people, preserving national sovereignty and security, and strengthening private property protection. Economic development and liberalization are central to the strategy, as they drive the country's internal transformation as well as an active, pragmatic foreign policy.

Central Asia: A Cornerstone of Uzbekistan’s Foreign Policy

The fifth pillar of the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, titled “Consistent continuation of the policy based on the principle of a safe and peace-loving state,” encompasses goals 90–100.²⁸ These objectives emphasize fostering strategic alliances within Central Asia and expanding multifaceted cooperation with long-standing partners.

Goal 91 prioritizes elevating cooperation in Central Asia to a new level. This includes: strengthening partnerships with neighbouring countries; deepening strategic alliances; facilitating the free movement of citizens, goods, services, and capital; creating a shared regional tourism space; supporting Afghanistan’s economic recovery through mutual engagement.

In recent years, Uzbekistan’s focus on fostering friendly and mutually beneficial relations with its Central Asian neighbours has transformed regional dynamics. This has been evident in the establishment of consultative meetings

²⁷ The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy”, PF-158 (2023). <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6600413>

²⁸ Development Strategy Center (2023). “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy. <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=1907>

among Central Asian heads of state, an increase in official bilateral visits, and the restoration of transport links.

Additionally, significant progress has been made in resolving long-standing regional challenges, such as water management, border disputes, and transportation issues, which have historically hindered regional cooperation.

Uzbekistan's economic diplomacy has been instrumental in enhancing trade within the region. By 2023, Uzbekistan's foreign trade turnover with Central Asia had nearly tripled since 2016, reaching \$7.2 billion.²⁹ Total intra-regional trade among Central Asian nations exceeded \$11 billion in 2023,³⁰ with their combined trade volume with external partners reaching about \$225 billion.³¹

Bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and its neighbors have also flourished. Since 2017, Uzbekistan has established strategic partnerships with Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan, which have evolved into comprehensive strategic partnerships. Agreements on allied relations with Kazakhstan³² and Tajikistan were also signed during 2022 – 2024, highlighting Uzbekistan's commitment to long-term regional cooperation.

In this context, Uzbekistan's long-term regional strategy seeks to progressively elevate bilateral relations with each Central Asian state to the status of comprehensive strategic partnerships and allied relations.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reaffirmed the priority of Central Asian region in the country's foreign policy during a recent meeting with newly elected parliamentarians on November 20, 2024, at the

²⁹ Review.uz. (2024, January 25). *Infographics: Uzbekistan's trade with Central Asian countries in January-December 2023*. <https://review.uz/en/post/infografika-torgovlya-uzbekistana-so-stranami-centralnoy-azii-za>

³⁰ The Asia Today. (2024, March 16). *Trade volume between the countries of the Central Asian region exceeded \$ 11 billion*. <https://theasiatoday.org/news/trade-volume-between-the-countries-of-the-central-asian-region-exceeded-11-billion/>

³¹ The Tashkent Times. (2024, October 28). *Central Asia is becoming a major actor in global affairs*. <https://tashkenttimes.uz/national/13930-central-asia-is-becoming-a-major-actor-in-global-affairs>

³² Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On ratification of the Treaty between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Kazakhstan on Allied Relations" (Tashkent, December 22, 2022), № LRU-882 (2023). <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/6906583>

Legislative Chamber of Oliy Majlis.³³ President also emphasized the need to update the Foreign Policy Concept of the country and the importance of developing effective ties with key partners, as well as authoritative international and regional organizations.

Institutionalizing Regional Integration Through Consultative Meetings

The role of the Consultative Meetings of the Heads of State of Central Asia in forming basis for regional cooperation and institutionalization of integration of Central Asian States is important. During the fifth meeting in Dushanbe in 2023, leaders agreed to establish a Council of National Coordinators to oversee the implementation of agreements and propose new initiatives for collaboration.³⁴

The agenda of the sixth consultative meetings, held in Astana in 2024 encompassed a broad spectrum of topics, ranging from economic collaboration to security concerns, with each head of state articulating their respective national perspectives and contributing to collective conclusions and decisions.³⁵ In his address, President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev articulated the necessity of evolving the Consultative Meeting format to bolster regional integration efforts and to broaden the long-term partnership agenda among member states.³⁶ This summit was significant not only for the discussions it facilitated but also for the tangible outcomes it produced.

In pursuit of international subjectivity and unity within the Central Asian region, the enhancement of mechanisms for interaction among Central Asian States has emerged as a priority. The Roadmap for the Development of Regional Cooperation until 2027, signed at the Sixth Consultative Meeting, aims to address these challenges by improving intergovernmental coordination and reinforcing

³³ Official website of the President of Uzbekistan. (2024, November 20). *Time for new approaches in the work of Parliament and Government on the basis of faithful service to the people*. <https://president.uz/en/lists/view/7716>

³⁴ Tanbaev O. (2023, September 14). *How Uzbekistan Promotes Regional Integration in Central Asia*. <https://thediplomat.com/2023/09/central-asian-regionalism-after-the-5th-leaders-meeting/>

³⁵ Tolipov F. (2024, October 3). *One Step Forward, Half a Step Back: The Sixth Consultative Meeting of Central Asian Leaders*. <https://www.cacianalyst.org/publications/analytical-articles/item/13820-one-step-forward-half-a-step-back-the-sixth-consultative-meeting-of-central-asian-leaders.html>

³⁶ The Tashkent Times. (2024, August 9). *Shavkat Mirziyoyev's remarks at Central Asia Summit*. <https://tashkenttimes.uz/national/13500-shavkat-mirziyoyev-s-remarks-at-central-asia-summit-3>

oversight of the initiatives proposed during the consultative meetings. Additionally, another pivotal document signed in Astana, the Concept for the Development of Regional Cooperation “Central Asia-2040”, was designed to expand mutual interactions and strengthen the international standing of Central Asia.³⁷

Indeed, for all its light-touch approach, the consultative meetings have managed to create a firm and clear-cut set of fundamental norms and principles that define Central Asia and its denser intra-regional interactions.

By revising the strategic foundations of bilateral relations with its neighbors in favor of strengthening good-neighborliness and cooperation, maintaining regional security, promoting trade and economic cooperation, and deepening cultural and humanitarian ties with brotherly nations, Uzbekistan has managed to bring relations with the states of the region to a new level.

The role and efforts of Uzbekistan in the process of establishing peace in neighbouring Afghanistan are also noteworthy. In particular, at the initiative of President Sh.Mirziyoyev, one of the priority tasks of Uzbekistan’s foreign policy was focused on achieving peace in Afghanistan, and this country began to be recognized as a source of opportunities rather than a threat.³⁸

In this regard, a number of infrastructural and cultural-humanitarian projects are being implemented by Uzbekistan, which serve to establish peace in Afghanistan and regional cooperation between Central and South Asia. In addition, the delivery of the main international humanitarian aid to the Afghan people has been established through the territory of Uzbekistan.

The “Central Asia Plus” Multilateral Cooperation Platform

The State program and targeted indicators for 2023-2024 to be implemented in the framework of the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy have defined the country’s

³⁷Zafar A. (2024, August 30). *Summit of Central Asian Leaders to Forge Regional Cooperation Mechanisms*.
https://www.icwa.in/show_content.php?lang=1&level=3&ls_id=11724&lid=7130

³⁸SOCIETY Magazin. (2023, August 1). *Interview: Uzbekistan’s Journey to Progress & Prosperity*.
<https://www.society.at/interview-uzbekistans-journey-to-progress-prosperity/>

active and regular participation in summits within the “Central Asia plus” multilateral cooperation format.³⁹

Uzbekistan's well-thought-out, mutually beneficial, and pragmatic foreign policy has elevated its relations with leading foreign countries, rapidly developing political-diplomatic, trade-economic, socio-humanitarian, and strategic cooperation. Since 2017, international partners have increasingly focused on developing relations with Central Asian countries through the “Central Asia plus” (C5+1) multilateral platform. This platform, initiated by Japan in 2004 and South Korea in 2007, includes five Central Asian states (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan) and an external partner country at the ministerial level.

Notably, since 2022, ministerial “Central Asia plus” meetings have progressed to “summit” – presidential level,⁴⁰ involving heads of state and governments. Throughout 2022-2023, effective summits were held with the leadership of China, India, Russia, the European Union (EU), the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), the United States, and Germany with whom the second “C5+1” summit was held in Astana this year. Moreover, in 2025, Uzbekistan is set to host two summits in the “C5+1” format with the EU and GCC.

The “Central Asia plus” format has evolved into a significant multilateral dialogue platform, facilitating the development of mutually beneficial relations and collaborative proposals on pressing issues among regional states and major international partners. The success of these summits and meetings can be attributed to Uzbekistan’s active and pragmatic regional policy, which has elevated regional interaction among Central Asian states to unprecedented levels.

Uzbekistan’s Bilateral Strategic Partnerships and Multilateral Diplomacy

³⁹ On measures to implement the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy in 2023 in a timely manner, PQ-300 (2023). <https://lex.uz/docs/-6600390>

⁴⁰ Khakimov F. (2024, February 7). “Central Asia plus” Format of Multilateral Cooperation and Uzbekistan’s Regional Policy. http://cias.ac.kr/issue/45?page=4&me_code=3040

Uzbekistan's foreign policy extends beyond Central Asia, encompassing robust diplomatic, economic, and cultural relations with Europe, the Americas, the Caucasus, Southeast Asia, the Arab world, and the Indo-Pacific. Goal 92 of the “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy emphasizes development of mutually beneficial relationships with traditional partners, expansion of the geography of international cooperation, joining global production and supply chains.

Uzbekistan has also demonstrated its commitment to multilateral diplomacy by actively participating in over 100 international organizations and implementing over 140 joint programs.⁴¹ Its chairmanship of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Organization of Turkic States, and the Economic Cooperation Organization in 2022–2023 further highlights its leadership role in regional and global forums.

Uzbekistan's active foreign policy, in addition to increasing the international prestige of the country, serves to make Central Asia a stable and attractive region with great opportunities.

Indeed, Uzbekistan's active and pragmatic regional policy under President Mirziyoyev has transformed Central Asia into a more integrated and collaborative region. This shift has not only enhanced Uzbekistan's standing in the international arena but also contributed to the region's overall stability and development.

Uzbekistan's commitment to regional stability is also evident in its mediation efforts in Afghanistan. By hosting international conferences and engaging in diplomatic dialogues, Uzbekistan has positioned itself as a key player in promoting peace and reconstruction efforts in Afghanistan, which directly impacts the stability and security of Central Asia.

As geopolitical dynamics in the region evolve, Uzbekistan's commitment to fostering regional collaboration, balancing external influences, and promoting sustainable development will remain crucial. Through the “Uzbekistan – 2030”

⁴¹ Development Strategy Center (2023). “Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy. <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=1907>

Strategy and platforms such as “Central Asia Plus”, Uzbekistan is shaping a more integrated, prosperous, and stable Central Asia.